

Garret Thomas Kaess Applies for German Citizenship by Brian Paul Kaess

Genau! Around July, 2024, Garret Thomas Kaess received a receipt for an Application for German Citizenship based on descent from his father Gerd Edwin Paul Kaess, aka 'Gert Kaess' in America. Applications like these can be in the 'pipeline' for two-three years before they bear fruit, but at least there may be sunlight at the end of the rainbow! I know that when we grew up without a father, it was a *nadir* for us for awhile, until we began having families of our own. Now, our dad Gerd must be looking down from Heaven, smiling at his twins Garret & Brian, for helping each other. It was through Garret's own efforts and toil, the able abilities of his German attorney at *Schlun & Elseven* (Dusseldorf, Germany), and my own token contribution, that he was able to document and submit this application to the Foreign Ministry.

I hope that if he is successful in this endeavor, he will take this opportunity to visit the *Heimat* of the Kaess family: Benningen am Neckar. Perhaps he will have mercy on his family in Europe, and make a decision to finally visit them there. Also, he should look at his chances for learning more about German language & culture, perhaps by studying at the Goethe Institute, either at home or abroad. That way, he can say: 'Ich kann gut Deutsch sprechen!'

He should also explore the uniquely-German concept of *Freizeit*, in contrast to his current corporate labors, which is similar to the VW commercial lyrics: 'Do what you want to do, go where you want to go, be what you want to be, see what you want to see....!' I guess Garret always loved his vacations, didn't he!

When Garret finally obtains German Citizenship, I will heartily congratulate him on that momentous day!

(P.S. Garret said he applied in January 2024, and can expect a response or decision as early as Summer 2026- party time! After that he may take a family vacation to Germany and even buy a property on the coast of Spain- no use paying all those lofty German taxes!)